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CODECO

Cognitive Decentralised
Edge Cloud Orchestration

D24: CODECO Ecosystem Community-building Report v1.0

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Executive Summary

The CODECO Deliverable *D24 - CODECO Ecosystem Community-building Report* refers to the work under development in Work Package WP7 and Task *T7.1 - Toolkits Exploitation and Open-source Community-building*. It describes the open-source and community-building strategy of CODECO and shows the results achieved so far. The aim of this strategy is to best prepare CODECO's open-source results for (i) exploitation, sustainability, and adoption, and (ii) building a community of developers and early adopters.

Therefore, this report proposes an open-source and community-building strategy that addresses the specific challenges of successful open-source in collaborative research projects, where different organisations with different knowledge and attitudes towards open-source join forces for a limited period of time (rf. to sub-section 2.1).

As described in **Section 2** (rf. to sub-section 2.2), this strategy should (i) map and keep track of the project's open-source landscape, (ii) create an environment that allows open collaboration from the start, (iii) implement sufficient IP management, and (iv) define community-building activities.

Then, **Section 3** draws the landscape of the current state of the CODECO Open-source Basic Toolkit, providing for each component a short description, its value proposition for developers and the plans in terms of open-source. An in-depth technical description of these components can be found in the CODECO deliverable *D11: CODECO Basic Operation and Open Toolkit* [2].

Section 4 describes how the best practices for open collaboration are implemented in CODECO through the Eclipse Research Labs - a combination of infrastructure (GitLab), processes and trainings to implement open-source best practices and increase the chances of delivering high-quality, professional open-source results.

As first step, in month two of the project (February 2023), the Eclipse CODECO Research Labs GitLab¹ has been provisioned and, by the date of writing, 35 developers joined the CODECO GitLab, while the CODECO public Docker hub repository² is available as well.

In terms of IP and License Management, the basic agreement for CODECO open-source is that it will be licensed under a permissive or weak copyleft license. By default, this includes Apache-2.0, MIT, and BSD-3-Clause, and EPL-2.0. 3rd-party license compliance will be checked semi-automatically on a regular basis, using the Eclipse Dash License Tool³, to be able to assess and solve license incompatibility issues as an ongoing process instead of as one big risky milestone at a late stage.

Section 5 reports on the initial community-building activities performed between July 2023 (month seven) and December 2023 included (month 12). After having a look at all CODECO target stakeholder groups from the open-source perspective, the concrete activities and their impact are discussed. These activities (e.g., EclipseCon 2023, Eclipse Newsletter) address the developer communities to create initial awareness about CODECO and its ambitions in open-source. **Section 6** provides the initial planning for the second year of CODECO, which will be reported in the next version of this deliverable (D25, December 2024). Finally, section 7 concludes the deliverable, summarising guidelines for the next steps.

¹ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

² <https://hub.docker.com/repositories/hecodeco>

³ <https://github.com/eclipse-dash/licenses>

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List of Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Meaning
ACM	Automated Configuration Management
AI	Artificial intelligence
AR	Academia and Research
CA	Consortium Agreement
CI/CD	Continuous Integration and Continuous Development
CODECO	Cognitive Decentralized Edge-Cloud Orchestration
CRDs	Custom-Defined Resources
DEV	Developers
EC	European commission
EU	European Union
EUs	End-Users
Pub	Public in General
GA	Grant Agreement
GOV	Government, municipalities, public authorities, and policymakers
HE	Horizon Europe
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
IRCEP	Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme
K8s	Kubernetes
MDM	Metadata Management
ML	Machine Learning
Mx	Month x of the CODECO project
NetMA	Network Management and Adaptation
OCM	Open Cluster Management
OS	Open-source
OSS	Open-source Software
PDLC	Privacy-preserving Decentralized Learning and Context-awareness
SDO	Standardization entities and open-source communities
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SWM	Scheduling and Workload Migration

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1 Introduction

This deliverable presents the CODECO open-source and community-building strategy that will be implemented during the course of the project.

CODECO is committed to deliver its project results as professional, sustainable, and usable open source software and to implement measures to build a community around these open source results. Therefore, this deliverable describes the efforts made towards these goals in the context of WP7, Task 7.1 (based on the technical work done in WP2 and WP3) from M7 to M12. This period is considered as the initial definition and awareness phase, during which the groundwork for the definition of the CODECO Open Source Toolkit is carried out and the first communication activities to raise awareness of CODECO and its open source ambitions in the relevant communities are carried out.

1.1 Document Scope

This deliverable is the first in a series of three, covering the work of *Task 7.1 - Toolkits Exploitation and Open-source Community-building*, from M7 (July 2023) to M12 (December 2023). Thus, it introduces the strategy and initial activities carried out during this period. Updates of this report will be provided in M24 (December 2024) and M36 (December 2025).

Naturally, the work of T7.1 happens in close collaboration to all tasks dealing with dissemination, communication, exploitation, and ecosystem building. From the high-level perspective these activities contribute to CODECO **Objective O5: To build a consolidated ecosystem, appealing to the different CODECO stakeholder groups.**⁴

1.2 Dependencies

In terms of defining the CODECO Open-source Toolkit, this deliverable is heavily dependent on the work done in WP2, mainly Task 2.2, T2.3, and T2.4 as these tasks lay the foundation for the CODECO architecture and the envisioned open-source ecosystem, as described in the CODECO deliverable *D9 - Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Initial Open-source Ecosystem Design* [1]. The second strong dependency is to WP3, namely Task 3.6 in which the actual integrated CODECO Open-source Toolkit is being developed and reported in *D11 - CODECO Basic Operation and Open Toolkit* [2].

In terms of community-building, this deliverable is strongly related to all other tasks of WP7 which rely on a well-defined, professional CODECO Open-source Toolkit for exploitation and ecosystem development. Furthermore, it depends on WP6 because alignment is needed with the overall CODECO dissemination and communication strategy (*D21 - Dissemination, Communication, Promotion Plan* [3]).

⁴ With a strong focus on developers.

1.3 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 2 introduces the open-source and community-building strategy for CODECO taking into consideration the peculiarities of research projects when doing open-source.
- Section 3 presents the CODECO Open-source Toolkit.
- Section 4 describes how open-source best practices are implemented to maximize the chances of creating successful open-source.
- Section 5 reports on the community-building activities performed during M7 – M12.
- Section 6 presents the initial plan concerning OSS community-building activities for year 2 of CODECO.
- Section 7 concludes the report.

2 Open-source and Community-building

The definition of open-source implies that source code is distributed under a license in which the copyright holders grant others the power to run, access, modify and re-distribute the software to anyone and for any purpose [4] [5], thus enabling the development to happen under an open, collaborative model. Throughout the years, the *open-source software (OSS)* development model has become increasingly popular around the world. Today, open-source components are the core building blocks of application software in most innovative domains, providing developers with an ever-growing selection of off-the-shelf possibilities that they can use for assembling their products faster and more efficiently [6].

Open-source allows code to be used (freely), studied (in full transparency), improved and shared (collaboratively). To achieve this, there are open source licences that comply with the open source definition and allow the software to be freely used, modified, and shared.

Because open-source is all about collaboration, the concept of communities is of major importance. Generally speaking, *“a community is a group of people united by a common identity and collective purpose who engage in activities together over time. Communities develop unique sets of shared values, principles, and norms that distinguish them from others and provide members with a sense of belonging. An open-source software community is a group of people united by the shared purpose of developing, maintaining, extending, and promoting a specific body of open-source software. These communities are often globally distributed—their members occupy different geographic regions and work across numerous industries. What unites them is their common vision for the open-source software project—as well as the spirit of camaraderie and collective identity that participating in the community affords them.”* [7].

2.1 Challenges of Open-source in Research Projects

According to a study by Ait et al. [8] *“a considerable number of projects [on GitHub] die in the first year of existence with the survival rate decreasing year after year. In fact, the probability of surviving longer than five years is less than 50%, though some types of projects have better chances of survival.”* While this study does not specifically address open-source results of research projects, the survival rate of code on GitHub resulting from research projects is not much higher than what was found in this study.

Looking at the software industry, open source is ubiquitous and has become an integral part of leading companies' business strategies and products, as corroborated by several examples [9], [10], [11], [12] and best practices [13], [14]. However, introducing an open-source strategy in a company is still not an easy task and can be a long process; but once the decision is taken, measures can be implemented, structures and processes can be set by the management, etc.

Instead, a research project is not owned by a single entity, but consists of many different actors from industry, applied research and academia who agree to work towards a common goal (or set of goals) for a limited period of time. In terms of open source, the aim is to avoid the situation described by Ait et al, i.e., to avoid creating "*abandonware*" that is publicly available but has little chance of surviving beyond the three years of the research project. The nature of a research project as a collaborative endeavour for a limited period of time adds some complexity to achieving this goal.

Different organizations from different industries, domains and with different backgrounds come together with diverse ideas, beliefs, and experience regarding open-source. While some partners may have adopted open-source in their organization, this may not be the case for others. This becomes even more important when thinking about background and foreground of the research project. While some partners may bring open-source background into the project others may bring proprietary software. This has an impact on the envisioned open-source foreground to be developed during the project and poses challenges in defining which parts of the project should be released as open-source to what extent. However, if these challenges are properly addressed, the unique setup of a research project can be used to produce results in open source that have an impact: results that are not thrown away after a three-year project; results that are built upon, reused, extended, continued and developed after the project is over; results that have a longer-term impact on research and innovation agendas; results that can lead to new business models, start-ups and growth.

Perhaps not all of these achievements can be realized in the scope of a three-years research project. But the key point is to turn the described challenges into advantages and **create a strong basis that increases the chances of reaching these goals in the long run**. To do so, a realistic yet ambitious open-source and community-building strategy has to be implemented.

2.2 Open-source and Community-building Strategy

A good open-source and community-building strategy should (i) draw and keep track of the open-source landscape of the project, (ii) create an environment that allows for open collaboration right from the start, (iii) implement sufficient IP management and (iv) lay out measures for community-building.

2.2.1 Landscaping

The open-source landscape should set the boundaries and scope of the project's open-source ambitions. It tracks partners' background and defines the output that should be released. It also identifies the existing communities associated to certain background and potential new ones. Landscaping is an ongoing activity starting from the proposal when the initial concept is drafted, continuously answering to these questions: Will the project develop new tools or products? Does

it aim to provide a full-fledged integrated platform? Does it aim to extend or contribute significantly to already existing tools that partners bring into the project? Or a combination of all of those?

It is important to identify and state as clearly as possible which parts of the project results will be open-source and in what form, answering the aforementioned questions. This will contribute to a coherent open source landscape for the whole project.

Section 3 provides this initial overview of the CODECO Open-source Toolkit.

2.2.2 Open Collaboration Environment

As the name suggests, open source development is meant to be done in the open. In most cases, it is not a good idea to wait until the end of the project to release code, because "*the code needs polishing before it can be shown to the public*", or "*it's not ready*", for whatever reason. Developing behind closed doors is an open source antipathy. It will slow the project down, and the effort to "*do it later*" will continue to grow. It will cause a lot of pain.

Infrastructure (i.e., a public repo) should be set up at the start of the project, and open source best practices should be implemented from the start. This will allow everyone to become familiar with open source development and will encourage knowledge transfer. It is a prerequisite for reaping all the benefits of open collaboration - something that should be a pillar of any research project.

Section 4 describes the implementation of the open collaboration environment and best practices for doing proper open-source.

2.2.3 Open-source Licenses and IP Management

As already mentioned, it is important to discuss open source licences. The consortium should agree on (the types of) licences for the project results. For example, to allow commercial use of the open source results, strong copyleft licences should not be brought into the project (at least not without prior agreement).

Moreover, as the project runs and code is developed, it is wise to keep track of all incoming IP and licenses. The aim is to identify problems as early as possible. For example, replacing a license-incompatible library will be much easier if it is caught early, rather than later, when a lot of code already depends on it. Typically, IP and licensing are not straightforward issues and require a certain amount of training, coordination and, ideally, tool support.

Figure 1 shows the license spectrum, ordered from strong copyright (or proprietary licenses, on the right) to permissive licenses (on the left), until the *Public domain*, which corresponds to an unlicensed piece of software.

Section 4 describes how IP and license management are implemented for CODECO.

Figure 1: The OSS license spectrum.

2.2.4 OSS Community-building

When an initial open-source landscape is drawn, relevant communities can be identified. Of course, these communities are defined by open-source projects that partners bring into the project, but it is always worth thinking about other communities beyond the obvious ones. The old principle “*don’t reinvent the wheel*” also applies for community-building: Building up a new community from scratch is a long-term, time- and cost-consuming process. As with software, a lot of open-source communities exist and tapping into those is much more promising than trying to produce the next big thing, especially in the scope of a research project. Whether trying to build a new community or interacting with existing ones, we will follow the “**FREE** your community” philosophy for successful open-source community-building:

- **Feed** your community: In order to create and maintain a strong and sustainable relationship with a growing community, it is essential to provide it with regular information on the progress of the project while documenting the different facets of the project. At the same time, these actions allow us to build a knowledge base on the project that is accessible to all those who want to learn more.
- **Respect** your community: As soon as some code is available, it is important to share it with our communities. Even if we are not yet sure of its quality, giving access to our code to people outside the project increases our chances of getting feedback from our early adopters. “Every bug report is a love letter,” says Erich Gamma. This is absolutely true. In order to get that reaction, our early adopters will have to be able to (a) find our code, (b) download it, (c) install it, (d) test it. And, finally, whoever encounters a problem, will then have to decide to (e) contact us to report a bug, submit a request for enhancement or a simple question. This feedback becomes a real demonstration of their interest in our work, and we should not disappoint them.
- **Embrace** your community: The communities are not waiting for us. We may have an innovative idea, but if we do not know how to present it to these communities, if we

cannot show them that we understand their needs and know how to meet them, we will miss the opportunity to attract them. That is why understanding them is essential. And the best way to achieve this level of understanding is to attend conferences, organize or participate in local events, interact with existing user groups and, last but not least, meet communities you are not used to meeting.

- **Engage** your community: At some point, it is necessary to engage our communities. Remote webinars, workshops, contests, or hackathons are great ways to engage them. Webinars, workshops, or a hackathon bring useful feedback in terms of how the project is understood, how the platform is used, etc.

Section 5 reports on the initial activities towards open-source community-building for CODECO.

3 The CODECO OSS Toolkit

CODECO is a software-based orchestration framework, interoperable with K8s, that aims to support a next generation of container orchestrators that can adapt, learn, and develop appropriate response and adaptation. The CODECO Open Source Toolkit describes the collection of open source components that can be used. This toolkit includes all components that deliver the CODECO platform as fully functional, exploitable open source software: ACM, PDLC, NetMA, MDM, SWM (see D11 - CODECO Basic Operation and Open Toolkit [2]).

The aim of this section is to provide an overview of these components from an open-source perspective. This includes a brief description of each component, its value proposition to developers, and the current state and plans for open sourcing.

Figure 2 provides a high-level representation of the CODECO components.

Figure 2: High-level illustration of the CODECO framework and its main components.

Detailed in-depth specifications of each component can be found in the CODECO deliverable *D11 - CODECO Basic Operation and Open Toolkit* [2] and the elaboration of the architectural design is provided in *D9 - Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Initial Open-source Ecosystem Design* [1].

3.1 ACM: Automated Configuration Management

Summary

ACM provides methodologies and tools that support automatic configuration regarding application setup and deployment across Edge-Cloud, for single and multi-cluster environments. Aiming to provide concrete setup, configuration, and synchronization mechanisms suitable for federated cluster environments, CODECO integrates ACM, which offers automated management mechanisms to support both cluster configuration and application deployment setup, runtime workflows, and resource management (i.e., considering also non-k8s environments), and, at the same time, to assure minimum human intervention.

Value Proposition

ACM will add support for multi-clustering and resource management at the Edge, efficiently, and cover novel Cloud-to-Edge use cases, explicitly. ACM is based on the *Open Cluster Management (OCM)*⁵ community driven project which is the upstream project for Red Hat Advanced Cluster Management.

Open Sourcing

ACM is based on the OCM community driven project which is the upstream project for Red Hat Advanced Cluster Management. ACM will be licensed under Apache-2.0.

3.2 PDLC: Privacy-preserving Decentralized Learning and Context-awareness

Summary

PDLC is the heart of the CODECO cognitive orchestration. It is used to provide a finer-grained orchestration, by developing estimations about the system stability, and providing those estimations to other components such as SWM (for the purpose of re-scheduling) and NETMA (for the purpose of network reservations). PDLC has a key role during the application run-time. Based on specific target performance profiles (e.g., resilience) provided by user DEV during the application deployment setup, PDLC i) generates combined target performance node weights based on data-compute-network; ii) generates node weight estimates based on the combined values, and resource status from cluster infrastructures. It uses this information to train decentralized learning models that aim to provide forecasting and predictions about future behaviour of the infrastructure nodes and deployed applications. The output of PDLC is provided in the form of Kubernetes *Custom-Defined Resources (CRDs)* which can then be exploited by other CODECO components, such as SWM and NetMA, to make more intelligent and insightful decisions in terms of scheduling, workload migration and resource management.

⁵ <https://open-cluster-management.io/>

Value Proposition

Further the intelligence of cloud-edge orchestration frameworks based on cross-layer context data and decentralized intelligence that generate exploitable insights and predictions.

Open Sourcing

All developments and sub-components of PDLC are being provided as OSS. Community engagement with the component is crucial to receive feedback about the provided context information and prediction models and adapt them to best suit the needs of the community end-users. The current version of available PDLC sub-components are licensed under Apache 2.0.

3.3 NetMA: Network Management and Adaptation

Summary

NetMA is an advanced solution for managing and adapting networks, with the primary goal of simplifying the configuration of interconnections and enhancing the flexibility of Edge-Cloud operations. It effectively addresses the integration of internetworking control to support a wide range of network environments, including fixed, wireless, and cellular networks that will be the basis for a mobile and heterogeneous Edge-Cloud continuum, which will have to be supported by CODECO.

Within CODECO, NetMA plays a pivotal role in handling critical aspects such as network software-defined capabilities, semantic interoperability, secure data exchange, predictive behavior, and integrated network functionality exposure through standardized methods and K8s APIs. Additionally, AI and ML techniques are applied to extract valuable insights from network events, enabling closed-loop automation and adaptive control.

Value Proposition

NetMA provides an improvement on the multi-domain connectivity, abstracting the local and physical location of the worker nodes and deploying and easy to use overlay. It also maintains a complete and updated view of the current state of the network underlay and overlay, enhancing the network knowledge that the network manager normally relies on.

Open Sourcing

NetMA will be released as open-source under Apache-2.0 license. This license allows us to keep the rights of the module but at the same time allows other potential partners to help with the maintenance and improvement of the module.

3.4 MDM: Metadata Management

Summary

MDM provides a common place where all metadata from systems, applications and data can be brought together on a graph. This enables sophisticated analytics to gain insights into the behaviour of complex systems, and to take action to report or correct that system behaviour. In CODECO, MDM provides an API that can be used to calculate parameters about a multi-cluster Kubernetes system to drive intelligent application scheduling algorithms. Examples of these parameters include how 'green' the energy used for computation is, how well workloads comply with predefined rules, and so on.

Metadata is provided using a JSON schema-based model that describes entities with properties and relationships between them. This metadata is provided by connectors that specialise in collecting metadata from specific systems and applications. These include Kubernetes clusters themselves, but can be enriched with metadata about any system, provided a connector is developed for it.

The metadata model can be fully customised to the needs of a particular use case, although reuse is encouraged to facilitate the extensibility of existing applications and analysis logic.

Value Proposition

Enable mechanisms to assess and control how complex systems in the cloud-to-edge continuum behave according to policies defined as queries over a graph describing the aspects of interest of those systems to the end-user.

Open Sourcing

The development of MDM will be open-source in the CODECO Research Labs repositories. It will leverage background assets from IBM-owned repositories that are also open-source. We expect the community to participate in the development of use cases, metadata models and corresponding connectors, with the goal of creating a rich open source metadata collection environment for systems analysis. All components developed by IBM in the CODECO project, and in particular the Metadata Management Module, are licensed under the Apache 2.0 licence, which is considered a permissive license.

3.5 SWM: Scheduling and Workload Migration

Summary

SWM handles the initial deployment, monitoring, and potential migration of application workloads within a single cluster and across multi-cluster environments. This means supporting the efficient (low latency, lower power consumption, data sensitivity, *Quality of Experience (QoE)*) placement of applications and their containers across the edge-cloud, derived from information provided either directly by the user or by other components, primarily PDLC (e.g., device and node availability; container centrality; network characteristics), both through a set of *Custom Resources (CR)*. For example, SWM handles the "best" placement (based on context-aware indicators) for the containerised components of an application to be deployed in a cluster, considering the dynamic properties of the available infrastructure, including physical/virtual machines as well as network nodes and links. Furthermore, this placement needs to be dynamically adaptable, which means achieving efficient (low latency, lower power consumption, data sensitivity, QoE) migration of containerised micro-services of an application across edge and cloud.

Value Proposition

Enhanced scheduling and dynamic migration of the workloads (pods) of distributed applications across the cloud-edge continuum, based on QoS and context criteria, completely integrated into the K8s framework.

Open Sourcing

The implementation of SWM is based on background IP from Siemens AG, an initial code base has already been modified and transferred to the CODECO project internal repository where it has been available to all project partners since September 2023 (M9). SWM is released based on Apache 2.0 license.

4 Implementing Open Collaboration Best Practices

4.1 Research Labs

Eclipse Research Labs is a combination of infrastructure (GitLab), processes and trainings to implement open-source best practices right from the start and increase the chances of delivering high-quality, professional open-source results (see also D9 - Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Initial Open-source Ecosystem Design [1] for more background).

Eclipse Research Labs aims at gradually and continuously preparing research results to become proper open-source projects during the research project lifetime.

4.1.1 Repository

In M2, the Eclipse CODECO Research Labs GitLab⁶ has been provisioned and at the time of this deliverable release, 35 developers signed the Contributor Agreement and joined the CODECO GitLab. The repository is structured following the components of the CODECO Open-source Toolkit (see Figure 3) and CI/CD is implemented in the scope of WP3.

Collaborative development in the public repository has started and the initial snapshot of the CODECO open-source toolkit was released in M10 (D11 - CODECO Basic Operation and Open Toolkit v1.0 [2]).

⁶ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

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Figure 3. The CODECO Research Labs GitLab.

4.1.2 OSS Licenses

As discussed in Section 2, IP and license management is an important part of open-source software development. Two steps need to be considered: The license(s) under which the CODECO Open-source components will be made available and compatibility with the licenses of third-party libraries used by CODECO components.

The basic agreement for CODECO open-source is that it will be licensed under a permissive or weak copyleft license. By default, this includes Apache-2-0, MIT, and BSD-3-Clause, and EPL-2.0. Use of other licenses will be decided based on prior discussion among the consortium members. Appropriate **copyright headers** will be added to all relevant files in the repositories accordingly. Copyright headers for CODECO will follow the Eclipse Foundation recommendations as described in the Eclipse Foundation Project Handbook⁷ and depicted in Figure 4. The headers consider the following fields:

- 1) Name of the initial copyright owner (this must be a legal entity); other organisations that have contributed are either listed individually or grouped together by appending "and others". The year is expressed either as a single year or a range spanning the year of the initial creation and that of the most recent change.
- 2) Declared project licenses described in human readable form.
- 3) Declared project licenses indicated using SPDX codes and expressions.
- 4) The names of the contributors and the nature of their contribution (this section may be excluded).

⁷ <https://www.eclipse.org/projects/handbook/#ip-copyright-headers>

```

/*****
 * Copyright (c) {year} {owner}[ and others] ①
 *
 * This program and the accompanying materials are made available under the ②
 * terms of the Eclipse Public License 2.0 which is available at
 * http://www.eclipse.org/legal/epl-2.0.
 *
 * SPDX-License-Identifier: EPL-2.0 ③
 *
 * Contributors: ④
 *   {name} - initial API and implementation
 *****/

```

Figure 4. Copyright header in the CODECO OSS code.

3rd-party license compliance will be checked semi-automatically on a regular basis, using the Eclipse Dash License Tool⁸ (short: Dash License). Dash License identifies the licenses of content. It is intended primarily for use by Eclipse committers to vet third party content used by their Eclipse open-source project. The Eclipse Dash License Tool does not identify dependencies (at least not in general). Rather, the value it provides starts after the list of dependencies are identified by build tools. That is, the tool works on the list of dependencies with which is it provided. The tool is only as good as the input with which it is provided, and it is up to the committer to ensure that the input provided is correct. That means, dependencies that are not automatically discovered by build tools must be vetted manually.

For any license-incompatible library found, the developer of the respective CODECO component is asked to exchange it, i.e., look for a library providing similar functionality under a compatible license.

4.2 OSS Best Practices: Trainings and Checklist

To facilitate the open-source work to the partners and to help understand the open-source best practices, during the reporting period (M7 to M12) three OSS trainings were provided by ECL to the CODECO consortium, summarized in Table 1.

Accordingly, to support the process of implementing the best practices, the checklist depicted in Table 2, will be used. It will help to monitor the state of the CODECO open-source repositories.

⁸ <https://github.com/eclipse/dash-licenses>

Table 1. Training on open-source best practices provided to CODECO consortium in 2023.

Name	Topics	Date
Open-source Ecosystem	Introduction to the main aspects of doing successful open-source including governance, IP and license management, community-building and infrastructure for open collaboration; best practices from experience in doing open-source in research projects	February 2023
Open-source Licensing and Compliance	Introduction to open-source software licenses; categories of OSS licenses and main features; license compliance and compatibility; recommendations for CODECO open-source components	June 2023
Open Collaboration, Open Development	Open collaboration; Intellectual Property and Copyright; how to develop in the Eclipse open-source ecosystem through Research Labs	November 2023

Table 2. Repository Best Practices Checklist.

Basic Information			
Item	Description	Comment	
Component Name	<i>Name of the component</i>		
Repository	<i>Link to repository</i>		
Owner (Partner)	<i>Project partner</i>		
Owner (Contact)	<i>Name and email</i>		
License			
Item		Comment	
License decision confirmed	<input type="checkbox"/>		
License	<i>License (SPDX identifier)</i>		
Repository Metadata			
	File	Checked	Comment
Required	README	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	LICENSE	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	CONTRIBUTING	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Recommended	CODE_OF_CONDUCT	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	SECURITY	<input type="checkbox"/>	
IP Review			
Item	Checked	Comment	

Copyright headers	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Activity	Checked	Last run	Status
Third party libraries check	<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>Date</i>	

5 OSS Community-building Year 1

This section summarises the community-building activities done since the beginning of the project, paying special attention to the period of time when task T7.1 has been active: M7 – M12. During this initial phase, the main goal was to set up the infrastructure to allow the consortium to develop in an open and collaborative way. Nevertheless, initial community-building activities have been kicked off, focussing on creating awareness about CODECO as a whole and its strong intention to make an impact with open-source. A first step into this direction, although not strictly a WP7 activity, was taken in WP3, when the CODECO Toolkit was defined (D11).

The CODECO results comprise five major assets of which three are most relevant for the open-source and community-building approach:

- **A2 Open-source Eclipse Repository:** A developer-oriented open-source software repository, to be available in an early stage of the project, thus allowing for early exploitation of initial, advanced results and a better adaptation throughout the project lifetime.
- **A3 Training Database:** Training tools and events, to support the development of services based on the CODECO framework.
- **A5 Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme:** Multiple community events, based on the different use-cases and including the different CODECO stakeholders.

Section 4 explained how the CODECO open repository has been set up in Eclipse Research Labs, in Gitlab. Along with it, to facilitate the adoption of the open-source approach by the project partners, several trainings have been provided. These actions have addressed the first two assets, A2 and A3, while A5 will be addressed in this section, where we will list the actions done with the main goal of engaging with the developers and creating a community around CODECO. This includes the following activities as described in Task 7.1:

- **Development of liaisons with relevant open-source projects and initiatives**, along with the interaction with the EUCloudEdgeIoT⁹ Research Community, as well as other European initiatives, such as HiPEAC¹⁰, and AIOTI¹¹.
- **Participation in OSS community events**, e.g., EclipseCon 2023, RedHat Summit.
- **Production of open-source specific communication materials** (logo, posters, stickers, etc.), contribution to the relevant channels (social media, blog, Eclipse newsletter) and preparation of future events such as the CODECO DemoCamp/Hackathon (M21-M22).

⁹ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://www.hipeac.net/>

¹¹ <https://aioti.eu/>

These task objectives have been addressed, as will be shown in section 5.2 where the communication activities and events done during this first year are displayed. The Hackathon/Demo Camp is planned to take place at the end of year 2 (M21-M22). It will be explained in the next version of this Deliverable D24, due M24. Section 5.1 will put the CODECO target groups in the perspective of open-source.

5.1 Target Communities

CODECO has defined in its GA the target stakeholders. For the purpose of outreach, the CODECO deliverable D21 (dissemination & communication plan) explains the key activities planned for each target stakeholder group. These groups, from their own perspectives, may be interested in the open-source part of the project:

- **Information and communication technologies (ICT):** Industrial and small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) players; vendors and integrators, service providers and telecommunications operators.
For ICT companies, open-source is a means to save money, resources, attract developers and foster innovation. ICT will keep an eye on the available open-source tools for their own projects, products, or services.
- **Government, municipalities, public authorities, and policymakers (GOV):** A wide group of public sector stakeholders including government agencies, regulators, municipalities, citizens, public authorities, and other organizations.
For GOV it is important to build knowledge regarding open-source to address the need for vendor-neutral public infrastructure, to avoid vendor-lock in and reach some degree of digital sovereignty.
- **Standardization entities and open-source communities (SDO):** Standardization entities responsible for defining and maintaining standards for various industries and technologies.
Normative, pre-normative entities and with open-source alliances and consortia will collaborate on the development and adoption of innovative technologies and open-source software, relevant to the CODECO ecosystem.
- **Academic and research (AR):** Research scientists, teachers, and students in the field of computer science, engineering, and related disciplines. AR are a key group to spread the benefits of the CODECO concept.
It is key to educate the next generation IT experts and equip them with the open-source skills required for careers in industry and academia alike. CODECO will be a vehicle to perform this kind of education and vice-versa benefit from the innovation potential that is inherent to this stakeholder group.
- **End-users (EUS):** The public and specific end-users in the use-case domains, including consumers, who are interested in learning about the latest developments in Edge-Cloud computing and IoT and how these technologies will impact their lives.
CODECO open-source results may be exploited in future products or services for EUS. It allows them to freely experiment with the latest innovations.
- **Developers (DEV):** Software developers and early developers with whom CODECO shall interact via the activities developed in, among others, WP7 (community-building, Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme for third-party engagement) will be considered to promote and evaluate the CODECO toolkit and accelerate the integration of knowledge.
Software developers are the key target group when aiming to build a community of open-source developers around CODECO.

- **Public in General (Pub):** General audience may also be considered as stakeholders of CODECO. Even without a specialized background in the technical areas of the project, they may still be interested in CODECO and understanding its potential implications for society. *Evangelizing about open-source and creating interest and knowledge in the general public is important and doing so by communicating about publicly funded innovations such as CODECO is a must.*

Among these groups defined as target audience, the community-building activities are developed with the main focus on two groups, **open-source communities (SDO)** and **developers (DEV)** and keeping in mind also the other relevant groups as **ICT**, **GOV** or **EUS**.

We have already put effort explaining it in this document in Section 2, Open-source, and Community-building: open-source is inherently linked to software developers since it started; the creators of open-source were software developers (**DEV**), and this group requires special attention. When it comes to our CODECO research project, the same principle applies: “*Don’t forget the developers*”. This group has the capacity of making CODECO sustainable.

Most of the open-source communication activities and events done in CODECO so far, have been focused on the developers, trying to generate awareness about the CODECO Toolkit. The following section provides an overview of the measures implemented so far.

5.2 Community-building Activities and Impact

This section provides an overview on the community-building activities developed until M12.

Table 3 summarises the main activities performed in CODECO during the first year, under the “community-building” umbrella, with special focus to the ones implemented between M7 and M12, not only because T7.1 had started, but also because the CODECO concept and toolkit had ‘taken shape’ and were mature enough to be disseminated.

Typically, open-source community activities contribute to a range of communication and dissemination categories and related *Key Performance Indicators (KPI)* as explained in the CODECO Deliverable D21 – *Dissemination, Communication, Promotion Plan* [3]. The next table shows, among the dissemination activities for the CODECO project and their measures of impact listed in that Deliverable D21, the specific KPIs regarding open-source and the contribution to them from the open-source perspective.

Table 3. Open-source community-building activities held until M12.

Dissemination Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs (D21)	Lead/Contributors	Open-source contributions, year 1	Impact
Media dissemination	All	Dissemination of the overall project development via broad media, e.g., TV, podcasts, YouTube videos, public magazines, and journals	1 per year	FOR/ECL, INO	- Website (INO, FOR) Involvement in EUCEI (open-source, ECL, FOR) ECL Eclipse2023 CODECO video Zenodo community ¹² (FOR, INO, UGOE) YouTube (FOR) ¹³	Website: 250 visitors, over 600 views. Zenodo: 603 views across all documents; 313 with focus on the deliverables related with OSS. YouTube: 70 views on the first video, since mid.November 2023.
Press releases	All	Dissemination about the overall project development, results, and events	4 per year (multiple partners) reaching to over 500 end-users	All	Eclipse newsletter 2023 FOR online press releases Social network activities with focus on OSS (INO)	Eclipse newsletter: over 250000 subscribers. FOR press releases: over 200 views Social networks: 399 followers in LinkedIn; 91 in Twitter
Industrial Event	DEV, ICT, AR	1 Inception event, industrial workshop (M12) Organised by FOR having as main target industrial stakeholders and aiming at igniting interest in further exploring the use-cases in multiple fields of IoT/Edge.	>50 participants	All	Preparation of demonstrations, code, and presentations/videos for the HiPEAC industrial workshop on 18.01.2023	To be provided after event (18.01.2023); currently 44 attendees from 32 institutions in 14 countries.
Representation in events	ICT, AR, SDO, EUS	Disseminate CODECO results in different venues, industrial and scientific. Promotion of active participation and discussions on	>50 events	All	- EclipseCON, Ludwigsburg (Eclipse, dissemination), 16th October 2023 - Eclipse SAAM on Cloud to Edge Continuum (Eclipse, dissemination), 16th October 2023 - 6G CONASENSE workshop (co-located with IEEE	EclipseCon: over 460 participants 6G CONASENSE: 50 participants Mobiarch 2023: 20 participants

¹² <https://zenodo.org/communities/he-codeco>

¹³ First video added in M11 (November 2023).

Dissemination Activity	Targets	Aim	KPIs (D21)	Lead/Contributors	Open-source contributions, year 1	Impact
		exploitation aspects and community-building.			WP/PMC2023, 29th Nov, Orlando, FL, USA, organized by fortiss) - MobiArch 2023 (Goett. Univ, Telefonica - Workshop Chairs), Madrid, Spain, Oct 6th 2023	
Advanced training ¹⁴	ICT, AR, DEV, SDO	Transfer results and address potential gaps derived from interaction with the scientific community. Specific events and participation in community events, e.g., summer schools, Webinars, workshops.	>20 organized training events with at least 50 participants	INTRA/ECL	3 trainings provided by ECL: Open-source ecosystem; Open-source licensing and compliance; Open collaboration, open development.	All partners involved, average of 40 persons in each workshop.
CODECO Eclipse GitLab	DEV, ICT, AR	Re-use of OSS code	-	ECL/All	Early release of OSS code as defined in D11, M10	35 followers

In addition to that, the next subsections will provide more information, including the measure of impact, for some of those actions. For each activity we give a short description and assess its impact for CODECO community-building.

5.2.1 Media Dissemination and Press Releases

Having in mind the focus of OSS community-building, several efforts have been done, as described in Table 3:

- Across the CODECO LinkedIn space, partner INO has been driving several dissemination activities, covering OSS results of the project, such as software release, among others. The CODECO LinkedIn has a total of 208 visitors.
- The Website has reached 250 visitors, and 692 views. Visitors return to the Website (in average, 2.77 views per visitor).
- The CODECO Zenodo community has reached a total of 603 views/downloads, where 313 relate with the deliverables that are associated with the CODECO OSS components and architecture (D8, D9, D11).
- Different press releases have reached over two hundred views.
- The CODECO YouTube playlist reached seventy views on the first uploaded view since mid-November 2023.

In the context of this category of activities, we highlight the Eclipse Newsletter due to its broad outreach. The CODECO project was part of the Eclipse Newsletter in July 2023. The article

¹⁴ Advanced training activities in CODECO are to be started in year 2 of the project, T7.4. However, partner Eclipse has started advanced training internally for the consortium, to bootstrap an understanding of building results towards OSS.

gives an overview of the CODECO concept and architecture, also with regard to the intended open source results, and already refers to the CODECO GitLab repository. The title is "CODECO: Supporting the Edge-Cloud Continuum Via an Open, Cognitive, Decentralised Framework" and can be found on the Eclipse website.

Figure 5 shows the first part of the article.

The current internet evolution, with an increasing focus on the intertwining of smart, mobile, decentralized IoT services, brings new challenges to the deployment of applications. Applications and their components need to be lightweight, highly portable, and mobile, to run anywhere and everywhere. Secondly, there is a need to handle large amounts of data often with very different features both in terms of computation (processing) and exchange (networking), including those with low latency demands. Third, it is important to guarantee a smooth data flow, to allow for a smooth and secure integration end-to-end, across edge-cloud environments. Fourthly, real-time decision-making on where to compute and to store data must be supported.

CODECO, a Horizon Europe project, is attempting to answer these needs (Figure 1), framing itself as an intelligent and decentralized edge-cloud orchestration framework that addresses the existing infrastructure by considering data, compute, and network resources.

Simplification & Automation	O1: Reduce Edge-Cloud Setup and Management Time
Data-compute-network Orchestration	O2: Optimize Edge-Cloud Operation via a privacy-preserving data-compute-network orchestration
Security & Privacy Preservation	O3: Provide automated, privacy preserving secure management for multi-clusters
Openness & Greenness	O4: Support multi-domain Edge Cloud operations integrating openness and greenness
Broad Impact	O5: Build a consolidated ecosystem appealing to the different CODECO stakeholder groups

Figure 1: The key principles and objectives of CODECO

CODECO develops an ecosystem consisting of open-source toolkits, large-scale experimentation, training tools and events, use-cases across four vertical domains (Smart Cities, Energy, Manufacturing, Smart Buildings) and multiple events integrated into a unique Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme. The open source software, which is pluggable and interoperable with Kubernetes (K8s) will be made available to the community through the Eclipse Foundation.

A Novel Approach to Orchestration: Data-Compute-Network

CODECO will implement software toolkits suitable for smarter management of highly-distributed environments based on heterogeneous networks and by integrating mobile, resource-constrained devices. The CODECO components, illustrated in Figure 2, shall extend the management and orchestration of edge-cloud services with cognitive cross-layer adaptability and with features that allow for intelligent decisions regarding computational offloading and network adaptation while taking into consideration application and networking requirements, data security and sensitivity, as well as other context-specific aspects related to the data flow. CODECO plans to support both single cluster and federated cluster operations.

Figure 5. CODECO article in Eclipse Newsletter in July 2023.

Impact Assessment: The Eclipse Newsletter reaches more than 250.000 subscribers from the wider Eclipse ecosystem. The CODECO article was meant to be the first activity to drop the name "CODECO" and create awareness of the project in the open-source community.

5.2.2 OSS Oriented Events

Three main events have been held in 2023, oriented to the DEV, AR, and ICT stakeholder groups:

- **ACM Mobiarch 2023**¹⁵, having as chairs Tingting Yuan (UGOE) and Luis Contreras Murillo (TID), Madrid, Spain, Oct 6th, 2023. Targets were AR, ICT, and DEV. The workshop counted with a panel session organized by CODECO, dedicated to the architectural design, and disseminating the CODECO Eclipse GitLab. It counted with twenty participants.
- **EclipseCon 2023**, organized by Marco Jahn and David Remon, ECL, in Ludwigsburg, 16th-19th October 2023. CODECO participated on the research projects, with the purpose of community engagement. Targets were DEV, AR, and ICT.
- **6G CONASENSE 2023**¹⁶, co-located with IEEE WPMC2023, having as chair Rute C. Sofia (FOR), November 21st, 2023, Targets were AR and ICT. The workshop focused on 6G aspects, and one of the proposed topics was flexible Edge-Cloud continuum. It counted with fifty participants.

Out of the different events, we highlight EclipseCon 2023 due to the focus and broader reach.

In EclipseCon 2023, CODECO had the opportunity to meet the development community: more than 460 developers, architects, researchers, and managers attended the event. This event lasted a week, starting with a community day on Monday and ending on Thursday after three more days of conference.

Figure 6. CODECO poster and CODECO team during EclipseCon 2023.

Impact Assessment: EclipseCon is the leading conference for developers, architects, and open-source business leaders to learn about Eclipse technologies, share best practices, and more. The Research Booth is an opportunity to create the intersection between both the

¹⁵ <https://mobiarch2023.github.io/>

¹⁶ <https://www.conasense.org/conasense-2023/>

research community and the open-source community and again, to create awareness for the CODECO project. To this end, this activity contributes also to Objective 5.1 about creating liaisons to the relevant stakeholder groups, in this case DEV, AR, and ICT.

More than 460 developers, architects, researchers, and managers attended EclipseCon2023 in Ludwigsburg. As part of the Research Booth, CODECO showed a poster, where all the attendants in the conference were able to understand the potential of CODECO. Also, CODECO flyers were provided to people showing interest in the project, while stickers were produced, having good acceptance among the developer community.

5.2.3 Engagement in OSS Communities

In addition to the development of specific events, and participation in external events, CODECO has been involved in different OSS communities, contributing to the creation of OSS paths in Europe. This section summarizes the contributions held so far.

5.2.3.1 EUCloudEdgeIoT Engagement

The EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu initiative aims to realise a pathway for the understanding and development of the Cloud, Edge and IoT continuum by promoting cooperation between a wide range of research projects, developers and suppliers, business users and potential adopters of this new technological paradigm. The initiative manages six task forces: TF1 Strategic Liaisons, TF2 Open-source Engagement, TF3 Architecture, TF4 Ecosystem Engagement, TF5 Market and Sectors, TF6 Communications.

Different partners in CODECO are engaging across all TFs. Specifically, FOR is involved in TF1, TF3, and TF6. ECL leads TF2 therefore providing input from CODECO as well. ATOS leads TF3, architecture. Moreover, INO is expected to engage in TF1, TF4, and TF6 in the context of the CODECO Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme (IRCEP), which is to be started in 2024. Key contributions of CODECO in the context of EUCloudEdgeIoT are expected to result from its framework (architecture and taxonomy); OSS guidelines (TF2); use-case aspects towards SDOs (TF1).

Impact Assessment: For CODECO the EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu initiative is an excellent opportunity to interact and align with the cluster of similar European projects and share ongoing work and results within relevant working groups. Relevant is also the definition of taxonomy and the architectural view for the Edge-Cloud continuum where CODECO is involved. For the period being reported, in addition to contributions to TF3 (taxonomy, architecture), CODECO has engaged in TF1 in the context of developed white papers, and concerning its use-cases, and novelty concerning Edge/IoT applications. CODECO has also engaged in the first EUCloudEdgeIoT concertation meeting¹⁷ both on the project pitching session and also having been invited to the panel “*Resource orchestration and adaptation in the continuum*”. There were around 100 attendees in this session (rf. to Figure 8 for a view on the event).

¹⁷

<https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/concentration-and-consultation-meeting-on-computing-continuum-uniting-the-european-ict-community-for-a-digital-future/>, May 10th-11th 2023, Brussels.

Figure 7. First EUCloudEdgeIoT concertation meeting.

5.2.3.2 HiPEAC

The HiPEAC initiative addresses topics across the compute continuum from Edge to Cloud, HiPEAC is a network of around 2,000 world-class computing systems researchers, industry representatives, and students, so the AR, ICT and DEV stakeholder of CODECO. CODECO is organizing an industrial workshop in HiPEAC 2024 and is going to regularly engage with the initiative across different activities, e.g., summer schools via the CODECO IRCEP programme (T7.2, to start in April 2024, M16 of CODECO).

A first preparation towards addressing the HiPEAC community has been the preparation for the CODECO first industrial workshop which will take place on 18.01.2024, co-located with HiPEAC 2024, in Munich. The conference runs over three days and expects to attract over 1000 participants.

CODECO organizes its inception event, first CODECO industrial workshop¹⁸, with HiPEAC 2024 (18.01.2024). The event agenda has been prepared targeting AR, ICT and also the DEV community. It shall provide demonstrations based on the existing code; presentations and videos about the CODECO use-cases. It also counts with a panel involving two other projects of the cognitive continuum, COGNIFOG¹⁹, and COGNIT²⁰.

Impact Assessment: The event expects to attract over 50 participants. It currently counts with a total of 44 registered participants. The aim is to ignite interest across HiPEAC, which will then continue with other related activities, targeting the community, such as follow-up workshops, participation in summer schools, etc.

¹⁸ <https://he-codeco.eu/codeco-industrial-workshop/>

¹⁹ <https://cognifog.eu/>

²⁰ <https://cognit.sovereignedge.eu/>

5.2.3.3 AIOTI

The Alliance for IoT and Edge Computing Innovation (AIOTI)²¹ focuses on leading, promoting, bridging, and supporting collaboration in IoT and Edge Computing and other converging technologies research and innovation, standardisation, and ecosystem building, providing IoT and Edge Computing deployment for European businesses creating benefits for European society.

Several partners of CODECO, such as FOR, ICOM, I2CAT, are involved across different WGs of AIOTI. In regard to the targets of OSS, groups that the consortium believes are relevant concern the Horizontal AIOTI groups *Research and Innovation* and the *Standardisation*, and the vertical groups Manufacturing, Energy, Mobility.

The key aspects involving CODECO partners concern the development of a common vision towards IoT-Cloud-Edge, addressing relevant challenges over the next decades (Research and Innovation), and the application of CODECO in its use-cases (Standardisation, specific vertical groups) and other vertical groups.

Impact Assessment: The key aspect under work in AIOTI relates with CODECO awareness and the re-use of CODECO. Currently, the CODECO OSS is being considered across novel project proposals under development with collaboration of AIOTI, and with AIOTI partners.

²¹ <https://aioti.eu/>

6 OSS Community-building Planned Activities

Several OSS community-building activities are already being planned, being the proposed timeline until the end of the project illustrated in Figure 8. This Figure provides a broad grained perspective, where only the main events are highlighted. However, specific activities led by different partners which are already under development are listed in Table 4. These activities are therefore a complement to the plan and contributions already detailed in Table 3, and which will be revised for the next version of this deliverable, D25, due in M24 (December 2024) of CODECO.

An additional aspect to highlight is that CODECO counts with a specific community engagement programme under WP7, the CODECO *Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme (IRCEP)*, led by partner INO and to start in April 2024, M16 of the project. IRCEP counts with a number of specific events dedicated to community-building and community engagement. IRCEP will first be presented to the target stakeholders in the CODECO inception event in HiPEAC 2024.

Figure 8: Main OSS community-building activities foreseen from M12 until M36.

Table 4: Initial OSS community-building activities foreseen for the second year of CODECO.

Activity	Targets	Aim	Expected	KPIs	Lead
CODECO Development event 1: Dagstuhl seminar “Cognitive and decentralised Edge-Cloud orchestration: a data-compute-network approach”	ICT, AR	Discuss challenges concerning orchestration aspects and concerning OSS deployment.	M24	>50 participants	UGOE
CODECO Development event 2: workshop co-located with a scientific conference	AR, ICT, SDO	Ignite awareness to the CODECO OSS assets, in particular experimentation framework.	M24	>50 participants	ATH

Activity	Targets	Aim	Expected	KPIs	Lead
CODECO inception event: first industrial workshop	ICT, AR, DEV	The CODECO Open-source Toolkit and open-source best practices will be part of the CODECO Industrial Workshop organized in the scope of HiPEAC2024 (January).	M13	>50 participants	FOR
EclipseCon 2024	DEV, ICT	CODECO expects to attend EclipseCon in 2024. The format of the conference is not decided yet, still CODECO expects to be part of it. There have been discussions about organizing the Hackathon co-located with EclipseCon; it is not confirmed yet and will be assessed accordingly during 2024.	M22	>50 participants	ECL
Demo Camps/Hackathon	DEV, AR, ICT	In the IRCEP CODECO programme, it is envisioned to have a Hackathon or demo Camp	M21-M22	>50 participants per event	INO, ECL
RedHat research meetings (every month)	DEV, ICT	Organized once per month, RHT will carry input of CODECO	M13-M24	Participation in 1 event per month	RHT
DevConf.cz ²² , June 2024	DEV, AR, ICT	Open-source conference, June 13 th -15 th 2024, proposal being planned	M18	>50 participants	RHT
CONASENSE 2024, June 2024	DEV, AR, ICT	Workshop to be co-located with a European conference, planned for June 3 rd -6 th 2024. CODECO will have a section with demonstrations in the workshop	M18	>50 participants	FOR
AIOTI Signature event, September 2024	ICT	Participation of CODECO with a booth and eventual demos	M20	>20 participants	FOR
OSS events during the CODECO IRCEP	ICT, AR, DEV	Joint organization of events during the IRCEP programme, e.g., demo camps, etc.	M20-	>20 participants	INO, ECL

7 Summary and Next Steps

The first six months (M7 – M12) of Task 7.1 were about setting up the open collaboration environment, basic training and creating first awareness of CODECO in the open-source communities.

²² <https://www.devconf.info/cz/>

This initial phase allowed the consortium to, under the leadership of partner ECL, get acquainted with adequate OSS guidance; understand key aspects in regard to licensing; agree on a common OSS vision, and start preparing the next phase of OSS community engagement. The next phase (M13-M24) corresponds to a community engagement ramp-up phase.

Overall, the project has been evolving in an adequate and robust way its OSS assets and has started robust activities to engage the future OSS community, defining specific groups, and planning events that target the different stakeholder groups.

As next steps, the following aspects are the basis for the work to be developed in the next period, and to be reported in the next version of this deliverable, D25 (M24):

- to establish the best practices for open collaboration, housekeeping of the repositories including IP/license reviews.
- To identify and sharpen the scope of the open-source communities to address and intensify exchange with shifting focus from general CODECO-project to the CODECO Open-source Basic Operation Toolkit, with expected release in June 2024, M18.
- To regularly assess the state of the CODECO Open-source Basic Operation Toolkit in respect to the potential creation of new Eclipse projects or (upstream) integration with existing projects (e.g., RedHat ACM).
- To increase the impact and community engagement, via the CODECO IRCEP, and additional activities being taken in the project.

8 References

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